

Accurate Modeling to Characterize the Distributed Substrate Effects in SiGe HBTs

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Abstract—The applicability of a distributed RC model for representing the substrate parasitic effects in a SiGe HBT is demonstrated in this paper. In addition, the corresponding parameter extraction from S-parameter measurements is proposed, allowing to achieve excellent model-experiment correlation of the electrical behavior of the device's output characteristics up to 40 GHz.

Index Terms—Heterojunction Bipolar Transistor, Distributed model, Parameter Extraction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The requirements of modern communication systems put stringent demands on semiconductor technologies for providing performance at a low cost [1]. BiCMOS technology based on SiGe heterojunction bipolar transistors (HBTs) provides an attractive solution to address these exigencies, due to the inherent properties of the SiGe HBTs, such as low noise, high linearity, and low power consumption. However, these remarkable characteristics can be considerably degraded in the microwave range due to the influence of the substrate parasitic effects, which become more important as the operation frequency rises. For this reason, for advanced RF circuit design, the impact of the substrate effects must be correctly accounted for in the modeling of the HBTs.

For an adequate modeling of the substrate effects, it is necessary developing physically based models according to the device structure. For instance, in the present analysis it is important considering the buried layer ($n+$) (referred to in subsequent as the sub-collector), the depletion region of the sub-collector-substrate junction, the resistive nature of the bulk substrate ($p-$), and the channel stopper (p). A cross-section of the HBT under study showing this structure is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Sketch of a HBT cross section showing its physical structure.

Usually, a lumped RC equivalent circuit model is used to represent the substrate characteristics. This is shown at the

bottom of Fig. 2, which considers the depletion capacitance formed at the bottom of the sub-collector-substrate junction by means of C_{sub} . Connected in series to this capacitance, the influence of the inner substrate resistance, and the additional associated with the channel stopper and the substrate contact resistance are taken into account by R_{sub} . This lumped approach is widely used; however, it is restricted for application at relatively low frequencies since when the frequency increases it is not accurate enough, yielding errors when representing the output impedance of the transistor and the actual gain [2].

Fig. 2. Sketch of a HBT cross section and its corresponding equivalent circuit model considering a lumped model for the substrate network.

The frequency limitations of the typical HBT model are associated to the fact that it neglects the peripheral capacitance of the sub-collector-substrate junction and the resistive behavior of the bulk substrate, resulting in significant errors at high frequencies.

Bearing in mind the previously exposed arguments, in this paper a physically-oriented model for represent the substrate electrical characteristics, taking into account the distributed effects of a HBT is proposed. In addition, the corresponding parameter extraction methodology is developed, obtaining a significant improvement on the output characteristics of a HBT in up to 40 GHz.

II. EXPERIMENT

On-wafer two-port S-parameter measurements up to 40 GHz, using a vector network analyzer (VNA) and ground-signal-ground (GSG) coplanar RF probes with a pitch of $100\ \mu\text{m}$, were performed to a common-emitter SiGe HBT, fabricated on p-type Si substrate in a $0.13\ \mu\text{m}$ BiCMOS technology. Using an off-wafer LRM (line-reflect-match) procedure, and an impedance-standard-substrate, the equipment was previously calibrated up to the probe tips, establishing a reference impedance of $50\ \Omega$.

Operating the transistor under cold-HBT condition, which is defined as the condition when the emitter-base junction and base-collector junction are zero biased, and therefore both junctions are depleted, results in a simplified equivalent circuit that allows an accurate characterization of the substrate effects. Thus, the device under test (DUT) was biased at $V_{BE} = V_{BC} = 0$ in order to obtain the S-parameters used for developing the model proposed in this work. Afterwards, the experimental data were de-embedded from pad parasitics by applying a three-step procedure and the measurements collected to 'open' and a 'short' dummy structures. [3].

III. PROPOSED MODEL AND RESULTS

The analysis presented here is based on the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 2, which consist of the extrinsic resistances R_b , R_c , and R_e ; the dynamic resistances R_{be} , R_{bcx} and R_{bci} ; the intrinsic base resistance R_{bi} ; the junction capacitances C_{be} , C_{bcx} , and C_{bci} ; the substrate admittance Y_{sub} , and the intrinsic current gain represented by αi_e [4]. Thus, considering that when the HBT is biased in a cold condition the following conditions occur: *i*) no potential drop is present at the contacts, *ii*) all dynamic resistances present very large values, (i.e., no transfer current exists), and *iii*) there is no current gain (i.e. $\alpha = 0$). Therefore, in this case, the influence of the extrinsic and dynamic resistances, as well as the current source can be neglected in the HBT equivalent circuit, resulting in the simplified model presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Small-signal equivalent circuit model for a SiGe HBT biased at $V_{BE} = V_{BC} = 0$.

Additionally, for a bipolar transistor fabricated on a high-resistivity substrate, the value of the intrinsic base resistance is much lower than $\text{Re}(Z_{sub})$, where $Z_{sub} = 1/Y_{sub}$. Therefore,

the influence of R_{bi} can be neglected in this case, simplifying the equivalent circuit to that illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Simplified HBT model in common emitter configuration used for derive the proposed substrate model.

where C_{bc} considers the combined effect of C_{bcx} and C_{bci} . Then, the constitutive parameters of the equivalent circuit illustrated on Fig. 4, can be extracted using the experimental Y-parameters, obtained from the corresponding transformation of the measured S-parameters. In this case, the following expressions can be written:

$$\text{Im}(Y_{11} + Y_{12}) = \omega C_{be} \quad (1)$$

$$-\text{Im}(Y_{12}) = \omega C_{bc} \quad (2)$$

Thus, plotting (1) and (2) versus ω , the values of C_{be} and C_{bc} can be obtained from the respective slopes, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Linear regressions used to determine C_{be} and C_{bc} .

In accordance with the model shown in Fig. 4, the substrate admittance (Y_{sub}) is related with the experimental data as:

$$Y_{sub} = Y_{12} + Y_{22} \quad (3)$$

For modeling the substrate admittance, it is important carefully analyzing the sub-collector-substrate junction. In this regard, notice in Fig. 1 that the boundary conditions between the depletion region and the bulk substrate changes as the channel stopper is closer. This implies that the peripheral capacitance differs from the bottom capacitance depending on the proximity of the channel stopper, and also on the variation

of the potential along the depletion region, influencing also the local resistance of the bulk substrate. In consequence, in order to accurately modeling the substrate parasitics in a HBT, it is necessary considering the corresponding effects using a distributed model, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Sketch of a HBT cross section and its corresponding equivalent circuit model considering a distributed model for the substrate network.

From [5]–[7], it is possible obtaining an analytical expression for Y_{sub} , this is:

$$Y_{sub} = \sqrt{\frac{j\omega C_{sub}}{r_{sub}}} \tanh(\sqrt{j\omega r_{sub} C_{sub}}) \quad (4)$$

where the total distributed resistance and capacitance, r_{sub} and C_{sub} respectively, are given by:

$$\text{Re}(Y_{sub}) = \frac{\sqrt{2r_{sub}C_{sub}\omega}}{r_{sub}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Im}(Y_{sub})/\omega = C_{sub} \quad (6)$$

The resulting model, based on (5) and (6), is shown in Fig. 7, where it is possible to notice a good correlation with the experimental data.

Fig. 7. Frequency dependence of the substrate parasitics for a SiGe HBT under $V_{BE} = V_{BC} = 0$ bias condition.

IV. MODEL VERIFICATION

Taking into account that S_{22} parameter is directly related with the output of the HBT and strongly affected by the substrate parasitics, the usefulness of the proposed model and extraction method is verified after performing a simulation using the equivalent circuit shown in Fig. 4, and evaluating the accuracy of the lumped and distributed models for S_{22} . As shown in Fig. 8, a very good correlation between simulated and experimental data is achieved when the distributed model is used, reproducing both magnitude and phase and allowing to verify the accuracy and consistency of the proposal for representing the HBT-output characteristics.

Fig. 8. Comparison between experimental and simulated data for the S_{22} -parameter using a distributed network for modeling the substrate parasitics in a SiGe HBT.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A distributed model for representing the substrate parasitic effects in a SiGe HBT has been proposed and analyzed. Also an analytical extraction method to determine its constitutive parameters, extracted from S-parameters measurements has been proposed. A very good simulation-experiment correlation for the output electrical characteristics of the HBT up to 40 GHz has been obtained, which is primordial for accurate circuit behavior prediction and circuit optimization.

The proposed model represents an important contribution in the field of physics-based equivalent circuit modeling since it helps to understand the substrate effects. Thus, the proposal can be used for improving the integrated circuit design, evaluating the process technology or optimizing the device structure.

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